

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of aliphatic alcohols by *N*-chloronicotinamide in aqueous acetic acid medium

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Kinetics of oxidation of five aliphatic alcohols viz. *n*-butanol, *n*-propanol, *n*-pentanol, propan-2-ol and butan-2-ol by newly developed oxidant *N*-chloronicotinamide (NCN) in aqueous acetic acid medium in presence of HClO_4 and NaCl have been investigated. The observed rate of oxidation is first-order with respect to oxidant (NCN) and fractional-order with respect to alcohol. A decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium increases the rate. Addition of nicotinamide (NA), has a retarding effect on the rate of oxidation. The corresponding aldehydes and ketones are the major products of oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols respectively. From the effect of temperature on the reaction rate, the Arrhenius and the activation parameters have been calculated. A suitable mechanism has been proposed and a rate law explaining the experimental results is derived.

The kinetic study of oxidation of alcohols is a useful and powerful method in physical organic chemistry. Literature survey reveals that kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of alcohols have been carried out using various *N*-halocompounds¹ and quinolinium bromochromate². But there is no systematic studies available pertaining to the oxidation of alcohol with a newly developed oxidant NCN. Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of amino acids by NCN has been reported in aqueous acetic acid medium³. We report herein the result of kinetics of oxidation of aliphatic alcohols with NCN in aqueous acetic acid medium by potentiometric method with a view to probe the mechanism of oxidation.

Results and discussion

Under the condition $[\text{NCN}] \ll [\text{alcohol}]$ the plot of $\log (E_t - E_\infty)$ (where E_t is the emf of the cell at time t and E_∞ the corresponding value at the completion of the reaction) vs time is linear ($r = 0.999$) up to 65% of reaction, indicating first-order dependence of rate on $[\text{NCN}]$. The pseudo first-order rate constant does not change with increase in initial concentration of the oxidant.

Increase in $[\text{alcohol}]$ has a slight positive effect on the rate, indicating fractional-order dependence of rate on $[\text{alcohol}]$ (Table 1). A plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [\text{alcohol}]$ is linear with slope ($r = 0.999$) less than unity^{3,4}.

The effect of $[\text{H}^+]$ is investigated by varying $[\text{HClO}_4]$ at constant $[\text{Cl}^-]$ (Table 2). The effect of $[\text{Cl}^-]$ is investi-

Table 1. Effect of varying $[\text{alcohol}]$ on the rate of reaction at 313 K
 $[\text{NCN}] = 3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, $[\text{NaCl}] = 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, Solvent = $\text{CH}_3\text{COOH-H}_2\text{O}$ (1 : 1), $[\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.3 \text{ M}$
[Alcohol] $\times 10^2 \text{ M}$ $k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^5 (\text{s}^{-1})$

	<i>n</i> -Propanol	<i>n</i> -Butanol	<i>n</i> -Pentanol	Propan-2-ol	Butan-2-ol
1.0	4.97	6.25	6.86	8.38	8.93
2.0	6.40	7.68	8.29	9.81	10.36
3.0	7.63	8.91	9.02	11.04	11.59
4.0	8.75	10.03	10.01	12.16	12.71

Table 2. Effect of varying $[\text{HClO}_4]$ and $[\text{NaCl}]$ on the rate of reaction at 313 K

$[\text{n-Propanol}] = 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, $[\text{NCN}] = 3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$,
Solvent = $\text{CH}_3\text{COOH-H}_2\text{O}$ (1 : 1), $[\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.3 \text{ M}$

$[\text{HClO}_4] \times 10^2 \text{ M}$	$[\text{NaCl}] \times 10^2 \text{ M}$	$10^5 \times k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$
1.0	1.0	6.40
2.0	1.0	6.81
3.0	1.0	6.25
4.0	1.0	6.51
1.0	1.0	6.40
1.0	2.0	6.76
1.0	3.0	6.73
1.0	4.0	6.57

gated by varying $[\text{NaCl}]$ at constant $[\text{H}^+]$ (Table 2). The effect of $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{Cl}^-]$ have no significant effect on the reaction rate.

Table 3. Effect of varying [CH₃COOH] on the rate of reaction at 313 K

[NCN] = 3.0 × 10⁻³ M, [Alcohol] = 2.0 × 10⁻² M, [HClO₄] = 1.0 × 10⁻² M, [NaCl] = 1.0 × 10⁻² M, [Na₂SO₄] = 0.3 M

CH ₃ COOH%	H ₂ O%	D	<i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)				
			<i>n</i> -Propanol	<i>n</i> -Butanol	<i>n</i> -Pentanol	Propan-2-ol	Butan-2-ol
50	50	37.50	6.40	7.68	8.29	9.81	10.36
55	45	34.75	7.59	9.44	9.21	10.94	11.77
60	40	31.50	10.01	11.48	11.26	12.90	14.16
65	35	28.50	11.67	13.26	13.69	13.12	16.73

An increase in the rate constant is noticed on decreasing the dielectric constant of the medium (Table 3), indicating the formation of less polar activated complex than the reactant molecule^{3,5} and it seems that $r_{\#}^3 > r_A^2 + r_B^2$.

Addition of nicotinamide [NA] has been studied at different initial concentration of nicotinamide. It is found that rate of reaction decreases on increasing [NA] (Table 4). Thus added nicotinamide has a retarding effect on the rate of oxidation. Further the plot of 1/*k*_{obs} vs [NA] is linear (*r* = 0.985), indicating inverse dependence³ of rate on [NA].

Addition of salts like Na₂SO₄ to the reaction medium has negligible effect on the rate. The reaction mixture

failed to initiate polymerization of aqueous acrylamide solution, showing the absence of free radicals.

The oxidation of all the five alcohols are studied at different temperature (313–328 K), keeping other experimental conditions constants. The Arrhenius plot of log *k*_{obs} vs 1/*T* is linear (*r* = 0.987). The Arrhenius and the activation parameters are evaluated (Table 5).

Mechanism :

Under the experimental conditions studied, the possible oxidizing species are Cl₂, HOCl, H₂OCl⁺, NCNH⁺ and NCN in aqueous solution. The oxidation of alcohols by *N*-chlorosuccinimide (NCS) and chloramine-T (CAT) have been reported to take place through the intermediate forms of protonated species of the oxidant like NCSH⁺ and H₂OCl⁺.

Taking into account all the kinetic observation and the above facts in view, it is assumed that HOCl is the effective oxidizing species⁶ in the present investigation. Addition of nicotinamide decreases the rate of oxidation. This retardation effect suggests involvement of pre-equilibrium step in which nicotinamide is formed. The following mechanism is proposed for the oxidation of aliphatic alcohols by NCN.

Table 4. Effect of varying [nicotinamide] on the rate of reaction at 313 K

[NCN] = 3.0 × 10⁻³ M, [*n*-Propanol] = 2 × 10⁻² M, [HClO₄] = 1 × 10⁻² M, [NaCl] = 1 × 10⁻² M, Solvent = CH₃COOH–H₂O (1 : 1), [Na₂SO₄] = 0.3 M

[NA] × 10 ³ M	10 ⁵ × <i>k</i> _{obs} (s ⁻¹)
0	6.40
1.0	5.78
2.0	5.02
3.0	4.45
4.0	4.12

Table 5. Temperature dependence and activation parameters at 313 K for the oxidation of alcohols by NCN

[Alcohol] = 2 × 10⁻² M, [NCN] = 3 × 10⁻³ M, [HClO₄] = 1 × 10⁻² M, Solvent = CH₃COOH–H₂O (1 : 1), [NaCl] = 1 × 10⁻² M, [Na₂SO₄] = 0.3 M

Alcohol	10 ⁵ × <i>k</i> _{obs} (s ⁻¹)				<i>E</i> _a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ln <i>A</i>
	313 K	318 K	323 K	328 K					
<i>n</i> -Propanol	6.40	7.85	9.26	10.67	34.46	31.36	62.28	-97.19	3.58
<i>n</i> -Butanol	7.68	9.33	10.05	12.98	32.55	29.95	60.98	-99.19	3.03
<i>n</i> -Pentanol	8.29	9.93	13.16	15.65	31.91	29.31	60.54	-99.80	2.86
Propan-2-ol	9.81	11.21	13.30	15.72	28.72	26.12	58.55	-103.62	1.81
Butan-2-ol	10.36	12.05	13.84	15.98	26.04	23.44	56.97	-107.14	0.83

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 [\text{alcohol}] [\text{HOCl}] \quad (3)$$

Applying steady-state approximation to the active oxidizing species the rate law takes the form,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_2 k_1 [\text{alcohol}] [\text{NCN}]}{k_{-1} [\text{NA}] + k_2 [\text{alcohol}]}$$

The rate-law predicts the first-order dependence on [NCN] and fractional-order dependence on [alcohol]. This also explains the retardation in rate on the addition of nicotinamide [NA]. The addition of $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{Cl}^-]$ have no effect on the rate of reaction. The proposed mechanism is well supported by the moderate values of energy of activation and thermodynamic parameters (Table 5). The high positive values of the free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) and the enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) indicate that the transition state is highly solvated, whereas the negative value entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) indicates that the activated complex is cyclic nature^{3,7}. The activation enthalpies and entropies of oxidation of all aliphatic alcohols are linearly related ($r = 0.999$), implying that all the alcohols undergo oxidation by the same mechanism.

Order of reactivity and isokinetic relationship :

The rates of the oxidation of five aliphatic alcohols correlate very well with Taft's σ^* substituent constants⁸ with negative value reaction constants. The values of ρ^* at 313, 318, 323 and 328 K are -2.40 ($r = 0.963$) and -2.16 ($r = 0.993$), -2.00 ($r = 0.950$) and -1.68 ($r = 0.980$) respectively. This indicates that the transition state of the reaction is highly stabilised by the substituent *R*. The carbon atom thus acquires a carbonium ion character. Therefore, a hydride ion transfer from the alcohol to the oxidant is proposed. The order of reactivity among the alcohols is butan-2-ol > propan-2-ol > *n*-pentanol > *n*-butanol > *n*-propanol. It is seen from Table 5 that the activation energy is the highest for slowest reaction.

Such a reactivity order has been reported earlier in the oxidation of aliphatic alcohols by bromate⁹.

The genuine nature of isokinetic relationship was verified by the Exner¹⁰ criterion, by plotting $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ at 318 K vs $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ at 313 K. This plot is found to be linear with ($r = 0.994$) slope (b) equal to 1.16. This linearity of Exner plot is suggestive of unified mechanism for the NCN oxidation of all the five aliphatic alcohols. From the slope of Exner plot isokinetic temperature (β) is calculated using following equation¹¹,

$$\beta = \frac{T_1 T_2 (b - 1)}{b T_2 - T_1}$$

The slope (b) is greater than 1 and β (285 K) is less than T_1 . These results indicate an increasing selectivity with the increase in temperature and the reaction series is characterized by compensation effect between ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger .

Experimental

The alcohols (AnalaR) were used as such without further purification. Standard solution of NCN (m.p. 222°C) was prepared fresh in water and its purity was checked iodometrically. Acetic acid (AnalaR, Qualigen) was purified by standard method. Perchloric acid (AnalaR) was used as source of $[\text{H}^+]$. Sodium chloride (Merck) was used as source of $[\text{Cl}^-]$. Conductivity water used throughout the study.

The reaction was carried out under pseudo first-order condition ($[\text{alcohol}] > [\text{NCN}]$). The reaction was followed potentiometrically by setting up a cell consisting of a redox electrode (platinum wire was dipped in reaction mixture) and reference electrode (saturated calomel electrode). The emf of the cell was measured periodically using a Equip-Tronics (EQ-DGD) potentiometer.

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

The reaction mixture containing NCN and alcohol (3 : 1) were kept at room temperature for 24 h. Estimation of unreacted NCN showed that one mole of alcohol consumed one mole of NCN. The overall stoichiometry of the oxidation reaction may be represented as

A mixture of alcohol and NCN (3 : 1) was prepared in acetic acid-water mixture (1 : 1). The mixture was allowed to stand for 1 h in the dark to ensure the completion of the reaction. The solution was then treated with an excess (200 ml) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in HCl and set aside for 10 h. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was

filtered off dried recrystallised from ethanol The product had identical melting point with an authentic sample of DNP of aldehyde In similar experiments with other alcohols, the corresponding aldehydes and ketones were identified as their DNP derivatives

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